

Cross-Technology Interference Awareness for Multi-User OFDMA Scheduling in IEEE 802.11ax

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Abstract

Cross-Technology Interference (CTI) significantly degrades the performance of heterogeneous wireless communication systems operating within a shared spectrum. Traditional mitigation techniques, such as Clear Channel Assessment (CCA), often fail due to, amongst others, varying bandwidth and detection threshold. Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA), introduced to Wi-Fi in IEEE 802.11ax (Wi-Fi 6), allows multiple users to be served simultaneously using distinct subcarrier sets, known as Resource Units (RUs), providing enhanced flexibility in the frequency domain. This paper explores and evaluates several Wi-Fi 6 compliant methods for multi-user OFDMA scheduling with CTI awareness. Through simulations, we assess the benefits of different techniques in various scenarios, in terms of either total throughput or average latency. To effectively apply the mitigation techniques, we propose a methodology that incorporates CTI feedback from stations and real-time CCA per RU. Given that commercial Wi-Fi 6 access points lack control over low-level OFDMA features, we use *openwifi*, a full-stack Wi-Fi transceiver running on software-defined radio, to implement the CTI-aware OFDMA scheduler. Real-life experiments validate the effectiveness of the scheduler and confirm its real-time performance capabilities.

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1. Introduction

Unlicensed radio spectrum bands have become more and more crowded due to the increase in Internet of Things (IoT) devices, reaching an expected number of more than 40 billion devices by 2030 [1]. Various different wireless technologies, like Wi-Fi, Bluetooth or Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), ZigBee, WirelessHART, 6TiSCH and, more recently, Thread, are sharing the same 2.4GHz band¹. Devices like microwaves, wireless keyboards, cordless phones and baby monitors also operate—often with proprietary protocols—in this band. Despite the availability of newer Wi-Fi standards in the 5GHz and 6GHz bands, the 2.4GHz band remains very attractive because of its greater coverage range and compatibility with legacy devices. Moreover, even in the 5GHz and 6GHz band, next to Wi-Fi, unlicensed use of cellular networks, as well as radar applications, satellite communications and other proprietary protocols take place. Furthermore, the Bluetooth SIG is targeting the 6GHz band for BLE also [2]. Therefore, Cross-Technology Interference (CTI), which may significantly impact the throughput and latency of wireless links, is and will likely remain an important problem. Currently, several mitigation techniques are in place, but these usually cannot fully overcome the CTI.

The IEEE 802.11ax standard (Wi-Fi 6) introduced Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access (OFDMA) for Wireless Local Area Networks (WLANs), allowing multiple users to be served simultaneously whereby each user is allocated a different set of subcarriers, called a Resource Unit (RU). This reduces the number of contentions to access the medium and limits the overhead of the preamble, thereby potentially lowering the latency and increasing throughput. The standard prescribes how OFDMA operates, but the scheduling of RUs, including their spectral width, location, individual transmit power and modulation and coding scheme (MCS), is left to vendors to implement. This flexibility in the frequency domain adds another dimension of freedom in the optimization of wireless networks, but it also increases

¹We will refer to the latter four, which all use the IEEE 802.15.4 standard, as Low-Rate Wireless Personal Area Network (LR-WPAN) devices.

Figure 1: **Wi-Fi 6 20 MHz RU locations.** Locations of the RUs in 20 MHz bandwidth for IEEE 802.11ax (adapted from [3]).

its complexity.

For downlink packets, the RU allocation is denoted in the preamble, while for uplink packets, the AP first needs to send a trigger frame, which informs STAs which RU they need to use. The available RU locations for a 20 MHz channel are shown in Figure 1. Note that a mixture of RU sizes can be used to fill the bandwidth, but not all possible configurations are allowed. For a 20 MHz Single-Input Single-Output (SISO) system, there are in total 30 different configurations possible. To limit the scope, this work mainly considers RU scheduling within a 20 MHz system, however the approach can be applied on Wi-Fi systems with multiple 20 MHz parts of the available bandwidth. An important aspect to consider is that an MU packet must end at the same time for all users. If the packet length cannot be changed, padding needs to be applied when the combination of RU width, MCS and payload length leads to unequal number of OFDM symbols among the users. This padding should be minimized to limit the overhead introduced by MU packets.

The concept of preamble puncturing to avoid intra-technology interference per 20MHz channel bandwidth is an optional feature of IEEE 802.11ax, and a mandatory feature of IEEE 802.11be (Wi-Fi 7). When applying this concept, devices will not transmit a preamble on part of the wide bandwidth to indicate this part will be left unoccupied, as such interference across different Basic Service Set (BSS) can be avoided. However, CTI from IoT devices generally uses a narrower bandwidth than 20MHz; for example, it is typically 1 MHz for Bluetooth and 2 MHz for LR-WPAN. Therefore, a more fine-grained interference mitigation technique would improve the spectral efficiency. While Clear Channel Assessment (CCA) may already help to avoid

CTI, using OFDMA, better mitigation techniques can be applied to further improve the coexistence of heterogeneous technologies.

Interference can have a disproportionate impact on performance, and since it is usually only present intermittently, it is not always captured in conventional channel quality measurements. Moreover, when the channel quality is inferred based on, e.g., packet errors, this may even negatively influence the performance due to increased channel utilization by using more restrained modulation rates, while this may be unnecessary if the CTI already vanished. Although interference is temporally variable and often statistically unpredictable, applying efficient, low-overhead mitigation techniques can still yield significant benefits, even if interference is not consistently present. We demonstrate that incorporating the notion of CTI into the scheduling of OFDMA frames can significantly improve throughput and reduce latency. Furthermore, we show that when performing a real-time spectrum scan and scheduling decision, an ongoing interference transmission can be mitigated, while minimizing the effect on the interferer’s communication.

The paper is structured as follows. First, we describe the problem of CTI in Section 2, and elaborate on related work regarding CTI avoidance and multi-user OFDMA scheduling in Section 3. Then we discuss our proposed scheduling options in Section 4, followed by the methodology to effectively apply them in Section 5. Next, we describe a simulation study when applying the mitigation technologies with appropriate scheduling in Section 6 and present the results in Section 7. Following, we validate two techniques experimentally using an implementation on the openwifi platform [4] in Section 8. Finally, we conclude the paper and give suggestions for future work in Section 9.

2. Problem Statement

The use of heterogeneous technologies sharing the same frequency bands inevitably leads to CTI when these technologies lack built-in mitigation mechanisms. Typically, low-power and narrowband technologies suffer more from interference caused by high-power technologies like Wi-Fi [5]. However, it has been shown in [6, 7, 8] that Wi-Fi also suffers from (ultra-)narrowband interference even when the received interference power is low. Especially high data-rate links that require a high link budget will suffer from CTI even if the interference power is low.

The likelihood of CTI occurring depends on the duty cycle of the technologies involved, where the duty cycle refers to the proportion of time a technology occupies the channel. The duty cycle depends on the type of traffic being transferred. Applications for IoT devices that require a high duty cycle include audio streaming, over-the-air firmware updates, and real-time control applications. In contrast, low-frequency periodic sensory data transmission demands a low duty cycle. In general mesh-based IoT networks could lead to high duty cycles for nodes located at central points that are responsible for routing the data. Due to hardware and protocol constraints, the theoretical duty cycle limit for LR-WPAN is around 66% [9], while for BLE it is around 85% [10]. Therefore, this paper covers a variety of duty cycles for the considered technology that acts as the interference.

A common way to mitigate interference is to avoid collisions in the time domain by applying CCA. If the channel is considered busy, a transmission has to be postponed until it is idle. CCA usually consists of an energy detection (ED) and optionally a signal detection (SD) step. It has been shown that CCA performs poorly for CTI, in the first place because CCA-SD is technology-specific. Next, since there is a fixed energy detection threshold, due to differences in transmit power and bandwidth between the heterogeneous technologies, there will be an asymmetric judgment on the CCA-ED unless specific measures for this are taken [11, 12]. The threshold of the energy detection step, which is set to -62 dBm for IEEE 802.11, will likely only be met by exceptionally strong narrowband CTI, since the measurement is performed on a much wider bandwidth than the CTI, making the time domain CTI avoidance based on CCA unreliable. [8] shows the actual CCA-ED threshold of commercial Wi-Fi devices varies a lot. For some devices it could not be triggered for a received power as high as -30 dBm, while others would back-off already at -90 dBm. Furthermore, the energy detection at the transmitter may not be a good indicator of the CTI level perceived by the receiver, which may create either the hidden or exposed node problem. Lastly, due to the difference in radio turnaround time for different technologies, one might access the channel when the other is still switching from receive to transmit mode [13], which eventually makes the chances of collision much higher across technologies.

When interference is present and results in packet loss, rate control algorithms tend to lower the MCS for the subsequent packet, which could reduce PER at the cost of a higher channel occupation time. However, it has been shown that rapid changes in channel conditions can severely impact the

performance of rate control algorithms [14]. Another downside is that the modulation on all subcarriers is reduced in a conventional Wi-Fi packet, even though only a part may be affected. Using Wi-Fi 6’s OFDMA feature, only the MCS of the affected RU is reduced, which increases the global spectral efficiency.

In short, the mainstream CTI mitigation methods come down to two categories: time domain avoidance by CCA and rate adaption algorithms based on packet statistics. Both approaches have limitations, as they were not originally designed to cope with CTI. The CTI mitigation problem thus consists of minimizing the impact of interference between heterogeneous technologies sharing the same frequency bands, while maintaining communication performance and fairness across them. This challenge persists because existing mechanisms such as CCA and rate control are intra-technology solutions that fail to account for cross-technology asymmetries in power, bandwidth, and timing. With Wi-Fi 6 becoming dominant in today’s market, the additional degree of freedom offered by OFDMA-enabled transmissions provides fine-grained control per RU, opening new possibilities for CTI mitigation.

3. Related work

In this section we discuss the related work regarding CTI avoidance and multi-user OFDMA scheduling, including channel-aware and interference-aware schedulers. Finally, we list how this work advances existing solutions in literature.

3.1. CTI Mitigation

To increase cooperation between IEEE 802.11 and IEEE 802.15.4 devices, several works have considered negotiation methods. [15] uses a busy tone to indicate that a IEEE 802.15.4 is transmitting, such that IEEE 802.11 devices can detect it. This tone is transmitted at a high transmit power by a different device on a different IEEE 802.15.4 channel, while residing inside the Wi-Fi channel. The work in [16] follows a similar approach, but the busy tone is generated by the same ZigBee device, which is able to operate in full-duplex mode. [17] enables the Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance (CSMA/CA) procedure between both technologies using cross-technology communication.

Apart from avoidance on the medium access control layer, changes on the physical layer are also considered for CTI mitigation. Since IEEE 802.11ax,

Dual Carrier Modulation (DCM) is introduced to increase communication range and combat narrowband interference. With DCM, the same information bits on one subcarrier are repeated on another one far away from it, effectively halving the number of data subcarriers. The decoder then relies on soft combining to obtain the processing gain. A downside is that it can only be applied to MCS 0, 1, 3 and 4. For IEEE 802.11bn (expected to become Wi-Fi 8), additional interference mitigation pilot subcarriers have been proposed in [18] to track interference, and afterwards mitigate it with receiver beamforming. A downside is that this requires multiple antennas on the receive side, and extra overhead for channel sounding.

Both [19] and [20] propose to mitigate ZigBee (which is based on IEEE 802.15.4) interference by nullifying some of the Wi-Fi subcarriers. [19]’s method is called EmBee (*Embedded ZigBee*), while in [20] it is called COFFEE (*COexist wiFi For zigBEE*). In both cases, it requires a modification to the physical layer of IEEE 802.11g. EmBee is evaluated by an implementation on the WARP v3 platform, and COFFEE on the USRP platform. It shows that EmBee improved throughput of ZigBee, with limited throughput loss of 12% for Wi-Fi. COFFEE shows improved throughput for both Wi-Fi and ZigBee as compared to a Time Division Multiple Access scheme.

Similar to this, the authors in [21] propose to use a special data encoding to lower the transmission power on the Wi-Fi subcarriers that interfere with ZigBee transmissions. While this is standard-compliant, it requires extra bits to be inserted into the payload, and it can only be applied to data subcarriers with Quadrature Amplitude Modulation (QAM), not to pure phase-shift keying. Furthermore, it only leads to limited reduced power, as the amplitude cannot be nullified completely. It is shown experimentally that using QAM modulation, it reduces the signal strength at the ZigBee receiver in channel 1-3 by 4 dB for 16QAM and by 8 dB for 256QAM. Moreover, the Wi-Fi subcarriers that experience CTI receive lower power due to the reduced QAM amplitude, hence the chance of Wi-Fi packet errors increases.

3.2. Multi-user OFDMA Scheduling

There are several works considering the multi-dimensional optimization problem of MU OFDMA scheduling with various objectives. The work in [22] considers throughput maximization while avoiding starvation, [23] targets to satisfy minimum throughput constraints, [24]’s objective is to minimize packet drops due to deadlines, while [25] aims for a maximum of 1 ms transmission delay in 99.999% of cases. Each of the different objectives leads

to a different scheduler, indicating that a generic scheduler will lead to performance loss depending on the objective.

In addition to OFDMA schedulers that typically assume uniform channel quality across the bandwidth, there are several studies that account for varying channel conditions per RU. The work in [26] includes channel fading from Channel State Information (CSI) feedback into the scheduler for uplink traffic, and use a variable power allocation per RU. The authors of [27] use a similar approach and also take the problem of rate control with variable payload sizes and padding into account. The recent work of [28] follows a comparable strategy and shows its effectiveness in experiments with OFDMA emulated using multiple 20 MHz channels. While using CSI is a valid approach in interference-free channels, CTI usually manifests as a boost in the magnitude of the CSI, while the reception performance is actually worse.

The works in [29] and [30] use deep-learning for RU allocation and MCS and power distribution, in which they take into account that Signal-to-Noise Ratio (SNR) can be different at each RU. A fixed RU assignment of 9 RUs is considered, for which [29] shows similar performance to the optimal solution as obtained by linear programming. [30] uses a deep-learning method to assign RUs to different STAs, and allocate the power budget of each STA among the assigned RUs. As a comparison, they also use a scheduler that simply allocates RUs to the users with highest SNR at those RUs. The deep-learning method significantly outperforms the simple scheduler, since it avoids that only a limited number of STAs occupy multiple RUs with limited power, but instead spreads the load across multiple STAs.

Several works consider the resource allocation problem in cellular networks when using OFDMA across overlapping femtocells [31]. By assigning different sets of subchannels to adjacent cells, interference can be avoided, which is referred to as fractional frequency reuse. However, it comes at the cost of spectrum utilization, but this can be partially overcome by applying appropriate power control.

A similar approach is proposed for the IEEE 802.11bn (Wi-Fi 8) standard, called coordinated OFDMA. Using this, intra-technology interference in overlapping basic service sets can be avoided by allocating resources to users of different BSSs simultaneously. For wideband interference (20 MHz or more), which is usually intra-technology, preamble puncturing as explained in Section 1 has been shown to be effective in [32]. However, the authors mention that the accompanying signaling overhead should be minimized to

obtain the best results.

In our previous work [33], we have shown the concept of puncturing an RU affected by CTI in a single-user uplink scenario where the interference was assumed to be known to the AP. Here, we extend this to a multi-user scenario and perform extensive simulations with other techniques also. Furthermore, in [34] we have shown a method to detect CTI and the influence of proper RU allocation to avoid CTI, but only in a single scenario. In this work, we extend this with a detailed multi-user scheduler considering different SNR, Signal-to-Interference Ratio (SIR) and CTI duty cycle, combined with a real-time interference avoidance methodology as explained hereafter.

3.3. This work

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first work that considers multi-user 802.11ax OFDMA scheduling specifically with CTI awareness. Moreover, our work avoids the limitations and accompanying loss in spectral efficiency of pure time-based interference avoidance. Commercial Wi-Fi 6 APs do not allow control of OFDMA parameters beyond enabling or disabling the feature, which is why we use an in-house developed software-defined radio implementation, specifically openwifi, for validation.

4. Proposed scheduling techniques

CTI-aware multi-user OFDMA scheduling can be accomplished in several ways. Our proposed methods are visualized in Figure 2 for a scenario where an AP sends downlink traffic to two STAs, while narrowband CTI is present. We will discuss the techniques hereafter and present in which scenarios they are especially beneficial.

4.1. Per-RU power boost factor

The first method is to apply a per-RU power boost factor, which can be used to overcome the interference. It is therefore similar to optimizing transmit power based on expected SNR as examined by [26] and [28], but now specifically applied to overcome interference. For MU downlink packets, the IEEE 802.11ax standard allows for a per-RU power boost factor, ranging from 0.5 to 2, corresponding to a power difference of -6 to $+6$ dB. When a station does not set the Power Boost Factor Support capability, the ratio between the power boost factor of different RUs can be at maximum 2 instead of 4 (given by $2/0.5$).

Figure 2: **The proposed OFDMA-based CTI mitigation techniques.** Schematic overview of OFDMA-based CTI mitigation options for a downlink transmission to two STAs: per-RU power boost factor (a), RU reallocation (b) and RU puncturing (c). The top and bottom figures show the situation before and after applying the mitigation technique, respectively.

To maintain the same average output power, applying a boost on a certain RU requires attenuation of the remaining RU(s). This scaling factor s_r for the amplitude of an RU with index r is defined as follows in the IEEE 802.11ax standard as part of Eq. (27-3):

$$s_r = \frac{\alpha_r}{\sqrt{\sum_{r'=0}^{N_{\text{RU}}-1} \alpha_{r'}^2 |K_{r'}|}}, \quad (1)$$

where α_r is the power boost factor at the RU, N_{RU} is the number of occupied RUs, and K_r is set of modulated subcarriers in the RU with index r .

The effect of applying a different power boost factor is schematically demonstrated in Figure 2a, namely STA2's RU will be power boosted to overcome the CTI it experiences. Similar to downlink, for MU uplink packets the AP can specify the target receive power per RU in the trigger frame. It can therefore enlarge this value for the RU in which it experiences interference.

Power boosting can only be used when the level of CTI is relatively low, since only then the packets may still be decoded by an increase of the power. Depending on the expected Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) and the MCS used to serve the users, the power boost factors have to be adjusted accordingly. If done well, this technique can lead to an increase in throughput and a decrease in latency as the number of packet errors will be limited. A downside is that boosting the power will have a greater impact on the interferer's communication.

4.2. RU reallocation

The next OFDMA-based interference mitigation option is the method from our previous work [34], which we will call *RU reallocation*. Since stations can be in different locations surrounding the AP, some might experience more CTI than others, especially when the interferer’s transmit power is low. Then, allocating an unaffected RU to the user that experiences the most CTI will limit the impact of the interference. This is shown in Figure 2b by the received power at the STA2 before, and at STA1 after RU reallocation. The biggest advantage of reallocating RUs is that it comes at no cost when there is no CTI, since switching RU indexes of the same width does not influence throughput, assuming equal channel conditions. However, it will only be effective for downlink packets when there is a significant difference in the level of CTI for the different stations. Furthermore, it is only suitable when there is an unaffected RU available with a bandwidth suited to satisfy the users’ traffic requirements.

4.3. RU puncturing

The next option is to leave an affected RU unoccupied, i.e. *RU puncturing*. For downlink, this is allowed as long as at least 4x26 subcarriers per 20MHz bandwidth are occupied. For uplink, there is no lower bound for the number of occupied subcarriers. When the overall transmit power remains equal to the case without punctured RUs, the average power on the remaining RUs is higher when decreasing N_{RU} , as indicated by Equation 1. This is allowed as long as the regulatory limit for the power spectral density is not exceeded, which is 10 dBm/MHz for ETSI [35] and 17 dBm/MHz for the FCC [36].

Compared to the data encoding method of [21], RU puncturing fully nullifies subcarriers instead of using the minimum amplitude allowed by QAM, which likely still impacts the interferer’s communication. Furthermore, the punctured subcarriers do not carry data, such that the Wi-Fi decoding ability is not impacted by CTI on these subcarriers.

In [33], we have shown that RU puncturing is an effective way to mitigate interference in a single-user uplink scenario, but the downside is that it decreases the bandwidth used, therefore potentially lowering the throughput of Wi-Fi. However, when allocating RUs to multiple users, the part of the spectrum that is left unallocated can be small and may be close to the bandwidth of the CTI. For example, with two users as shown in Figure 2c, going from a 106-tone RU to two 52-tones with one RU punctured at the right

Table 1: Summary of standard-compliant OFDMA-based CTI mitigation techniques.

Mitigation technique	Suitable scenario	Advantages	Disadvantages
Per-RU power boost factor	One STA experiences relatively low interference power.	Flexible signal quality to different users.	Stronger impact on the interferer’s communication and lowered transmit power to other user(s).
RU reallocation	STAs experience different interference levels.	No impact in case CTI vanishes.	Approach is limited to downlink MU packets.
RU puncturing	One or more STAs experience high CTI power.	Higher power density on remaining RU. Limits impact on CTI communication.	Higher chance part of the spectrum will be unused when CTI vanishes.

time and spectral location will increase the spectral efficiency. Or, for nine users using the 9x 26-tone allocation, only one RU needs to be punctured to avoid CTI that employs a 1MHz channel such as BLE. Additionally, the IEEE 802.11be standard will allow multi-RU transmission to a single user, which further extends the usage scope of RU puncturing.

Since RU puncturing leaves part of the spectrum fully unoccupied, it is mostly suitable for a relatively strong CTI, or when the impact of Wi-Fi on the other technology should be minimized. Furthermore, the approach is most effective when implemented in real time, since this enables the avoidance of ongoing interference packets and prevents inefficient spectrum usage.

Table 1 presents a summary of the different OFDMA-based CTI mitigation techniques. It shows in which scenarios they are applicable, their advantages and disadvantages. To examine the performance of each one quantitatively, we will perform simulations as described in Section 6, after we describe the scheduling methodology in the following section.

Figure 3: **Methodology for CTI-aware OFDMA scheduling.** An access point performs CRUA and receives CTI feedback from stations to perform multi-user OFDMA scheduling.

5. Scheduling Methodology

In this section, we will discuss the methodology for CTI-aware OFDMA scheduling. In general, the same mechanism can be applied for uplink and downlink CTI-aware scheduling, except that for downlink the AP needs to be aware of the CTI status at each station, whereas for uplink the AP only requires to know its own CTI status, and not that of each station. Another minor difference is that for downlink the AP directly assigns various configurations in its data packets, while for uplink, the AP needs to control the OFDMA parameters via trigger frames as specified in the 802.11ax standard. In order to detect interference and choose the appropriate mitigation technique, we propose to combine CTI feedback from STAs with a per-RU CCA at the AP. The methodology is explained hereafter and schematically visualized in Figure 3 with one AP and two STAs.

5.1. CTI feedback from stations

In order to ensure that the level of CTI at the receiver is measured, STAs will perform the detection themselves and report the result to the AP, including the spectral location. We have shown in [34] that the detection can be done using the CSI from regular received Wi-Fi packets, thus requiring no hardware modifications or additional overhead in the form of control packets or interference mitigation pilot subcarriers. The CSI consisting of magnitude and phase of each subcarrier is collected as input to a machine learning model, which produces a classification result representing whether interference is present, and if so, its type. Hence, the feedback does not consist of the full

CSI, but only the classification result. A detailed explanation of the model can be found in [34].

Note that for efficient uplink OFDMA scheduling, STAs already need to send buffer status reports to the AP. Furthermore, they may send Bandwidth Query Reports (BQRs) that include the busy or idle status per 20 MHz bandwidth segment. CTI classification is a similar indicator and the result of several CTI detections can be piggybacked in these status report packets to avoid too much overhead. For example, when splitting the bandwidth up into the nine possible RUs, only nine bits per received packet are needed to denote whether CTI was detected in the corresponding RU. If STAs do not regularly send uplink traffic, dedicated feedback frames will need to be used, for which the result of multiple CTI detections can be combined. For each RU, the feedback then requires a counter whose size in bits equals the base-2 logarithm of the number of packets received in the last period. When taking an average Wi-Fi packet airtime of 1 ms (max. of IEEE 802.11ax is 5.484ms [3]), this results in a feedback rate of only $\log_2(1/10^{-3}) \cdot 9 \approx 90$ bps per STA. Even with 10 STAs, considering an achievable Wi-Fi throughput of 40 Mbps, the overhead is only 0.002%.

There are some downsides to CTI feedback from the STAs based on CSI. Firstly, CSI is only reported for detected packets, a strong interferer may cause a packet to become undetectable, thus preventing the interference detection based on CSI to even start. To overcome this, the AP itself can also record the PER statistics per RU when it is alternating RUs. Furthermore, CTI feedback cannot be done in real-time as it requires receiving a packet and transmitting the feedback to the sender. Especially for technologies like Bluetooth that use frequency hopping, CTI feedback might not be a good indicator for any potential future CTI presence. Therefore, we propose to perform real-time interference detection at the AP as well, as explained in the following section.

5.2. Clear Resource Unit Assessment

Since each WiFi receiver will have a Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) module for demodulation, it could also be used to perform a spectrum scan in the working channel during an idle period. In this way, the AP can detect an ongoing interference packet, if there is sufficient CTI power at the AP. In essence, this is a CCA per RU, or Clear Resource Unit Assessment (CRUA) as we will call it from now on. It is similar to, but simpler than the enhanced CCA proposed in [11] and [12]. These works detect CTI based on signal

properties, while CRUA performs a fine-grained energy detection. Namely, just before preparing a packet transmission, CRUA will determine whether one of the RUs experiences interference by measuring its received power relative to the other RUs. For example, RU index 1 will be judged as interfered when the following statement holds:

$$\tau \cdot P_{\text{RU}_1} > \frac{1}{N_{\text{RU}} - 1} \sum_{i=2}^{N_{\text{RU}}} P_{\text{RU}_i}, \quad 0 < \tau < 1, \quad (2)$$

where τ is a threshold value, and P_{RU_i} is the average power of RU index i . The threshold value τ is typically set to at most 0.5 to avoid false positives, and can be adjusted if STAs report interference at a certain RU already. Note that devices will defer transmitting when the legacy CCA procedure considers the channel busy, but as discussed in Section 2, CTI is often not detected due to the difference in bandwidth and the relatively high CCA threshold. We propose to use CRUA on top of the normal CCA, and CRUA does not prevent the device from transmitting, but only provides input for the allocation of RUs.

5.3. Scheduling constraints

Using the aforementioned methods, the AP can now make an informed decision for the OFDMA allocation. Either using direct feedback from the stations or based on higher-level statistics from rate control algorithms, an estimation for the SINR not only per user, but also per RU can be determined. Note that this results into a high-dimensional problem, due to the following aspects:

1. There are many permutations for RU allocations and the RU distribution across users.
2. A mitigation technique influences the SINR per RU, which influences MCS and thus packet airtime.
3. The airtime per user should be balanced to avoid excessive padding.

Firstly, RU reallocation means each user could be assigned to any of the RU indices. For example, to serve four users, three of the 30 possible configurations in a 20 MHz SISO system (Figure 1) are valid, namely 4x52-tone,

2x52+26+106-tone and 106+26+2x52-tone RUs. For each of these configurations, we can assign RUs to users in $4!$ (4 factorial) ways. In total, there are then 559,413 permutations possible.² Secondly, given that RU puncturing and power boost factor alter the SINR distribution as per Equation 1, the decision for RU allocation and accompanying MCS would need to take this into account as well. Solving this optimally becomes impractical under real-time constraints. However, considering the payload length for each user and the maximum MCS bounded by a certain SINR, some heuristics can be applied. To avoid too much padding causing wasted airtime, the difference of number of OFDM symbols required for each user should be minimized, which limits the solution space.

Depending on the mitigation technique used, it can still be applied even if CRUA does not detect any ongoing interference to overcome CTI that starts during a packet transmission, or when the CTI level at the AP was too low to be detected. For example, using CTI feedback from the stations, RU reallocation can be applied without cost when no CTI is present. Power boost factor can be applied if the SNR for the unaffected users is already sufficiently high, or when the packet length requirements allows assigning a lower MCS to those users without increasing the packet airtime.

Given the objective and the scenario, schedulers will need to apply different strategies, which we will examine using simulations next.

6. Simulation description

In order to assess the performance of the different mitigation techniques in various scenarios with LR-WPAN interference, we will first evaluate them using simulations. First we will describe the simulation set-up, after which we discuss how MCSs are selected for different users, and how the mitigation techniques are applied.

6.1. High-level setup

We utilize MATLAB's WLAN Toolbox for IEEE 802.11ax waveform generation and signal recovery, as well as the Communication Toolbox for LR-WPAN waveform generation and decoding. It is important to incorporate the physical-layer aspects of the proposed mitigation options, since it influences

²This is calculated using the number of users per allocation as follows: $9! + 8! \cdot 4 + 7! \cdot 6 + 6! \cdot 6 + 5! \cdot 5 + 4! \cdot 3 + 3! \cdot 3 + 2! + 1! = 559,413$.

the decoding ability of different RUs at the different STAs. Furthermore, the SIR level and the exact part of the packet that overlaps with the CTI will influence the signal quality as well. Simulations that abstract the physical layer by a link-quality and link performance model, like what is used by ns-3 [37] or other MATLAB examples [38], are thus not sufficient. Therefore, we perform the full signal recovery process, which includes the processing steps a Wi-Fi receiver has to take. These steps include packet detection and timing offset estimation, coarse and fine frequency offset estimation and correction, channel estimation, demodulation, noise estimation, equalization, descrambling, depuncturing and decoding. For both technologies, path loss is applied to the generated waveforms according to the distance between the receiver and transmitter using the ITU model for indoor attenuation, considering residential areas without floor penetration. Small scale fading, i.e. the multi-path effect, is not studied in this work. In our previous work [34] we have examined that our CTI detection based on CSI can distinguish CTI from multi-path channel variations, and channel conditions are already taken into account by the works described in Section 3.2, hence we limit this work to combat CTI only.

To incorporate MAC-level characteristics, the IEEE 802.11 Distributed Coordination Function (DCF) back-off procedure using a contention window is applied as follows. Before transmitting, a device senses the channel until it is idle for a period equal to the DCF Inter-frame Space (DIFS). Then, it picks a random number from a contention window (CW) and waits this amount of slot times t_{slot} before transmitting. According to the 802.11ax standard, a typical Wi-Fi network's slot time is set to $9 \mu\text{s}$, and the DIFS is set to the Short Inter-frame Space (SIFS), which is $16 \mu\text{s}$, plus $2 \cdot t_{\text{slot}}$. The CW size starts at CW_{min} , and every time if one of the MAC protocol data units (MPDU) fails, it doubles, until a maximum value of CW_{max} is reached. When all MPDUs in a packet are received successfully, the CW size gets reset to CW_{min} . The CW_{min} and CW_{max} used in simulations are according to the best-effort access category defined in IEEE 802.11. The parameters used in the simulations are listed in Table 2.

During the simulations, the AP is aware of the decoding result of the packet at the receiver. Furthermore, we limit the scope to Wi-Fi downlink data packets from the AP to both STAs. For uplink, a per-RU power boost factor and RU puncturing can be applied as well, but RU reallocation will not have an effect since there is only a single receiver, namely the AP.

The LR-WPAN packets have a fixed packet length and modulation scheme,

Figure 4: **Simulation topology.** Two STAs surrounding an AP to capture the impact of different SNR (depending on d_W) and SIR (depending on d_L, d_W), as well as the difference of SIR between Wi-Fi STAs (depending on STA2's location).

which results in a fixed packet airtime t_a and are generated following a Poisson distribution with varying inter-arrival time λ . In order to investigate the impact of different traffic scenarios on the mitigation techniques, we take $\lambda = \{0, t_a, 9t_a\}$, which corresponds to an average duty cycle of 100%, 50% and 10% for the LR-WPAN traffic, respectively.

6.2. Simulation topology and scenarios

The simulation topologies are shown in Figure 4. It consists of one Wi-Fi AP and two STAs, which are both placed at the same distance d_W from the AP. An LR-WPAN receiver (Rx) is always co-located near STA2, and a LR-WPAN transmitter (Tx) is placed at a distance d_L away from the LR-WPAN receiver. STA1 is either positioned at the opposite site of the AP (as shown in the figure), or also co-located near STA2. The reason for positioning STA1 and STA2 equidistantly from the AP is that they should have the same performance if LR-WPAN is not present, to make sure the simulations show the impact on network performance solely due to CTI and mitigation measures if applied. OFDMA schedulers designed to cope with the Wi-Fi network's topology and traffic demand are already discussed in the prior arts mentioned in Section 3.2, which is why this paper is dedicated to CTI-aware schedulers.

The variation of STA1's location (either close or far from STA2) corresponds to the situations where either all STAs suffer from CTI equally or they are impacted differently. Both situations are representative in real-life scenarios, hence they are important to be considered in the simulations. The location of the LR-WPAN Tx is chosen such that by changing d_L the interference power at STA2 is changed. At the same time d_L is used to change

Table 2: Parameters used in simulations.

Symbol	Meaning	Value
$P_{t,W}$	Transmit power of the Wi-Fi transceivers.	20 dBm
$P_{t,L}$	Transmit power of the LR-WPAN transceivers.	0 dBm
NF	Noise Figure	7 dB
k	Boltzmann constant	$1.38 \times 10^{-23} \text{ J K}^{-1}$
T	Ambient temperature	293.15 K (20 °C)
B_W	Bandwidth of the WiFi transceivers.	20 MHz
B_L	Bandwidth of the LR-WPAN transceivers.	2 MHz
$P_{N,W}$	Noise power (dBm) at the Wi-Fi receiver.	$10 \log_{10}(kTB_W) + 30 + NF$
$P_{N,L}$	Noise power (dBm) at the LP-WAN receiver.	$10 \log_{10}(kTB_L) + 30 + NF$
d_W	Distance between Wi-Fi AP and STAs.	Depending on SNR.
d_L	Distance between LR-WPAN Tx and Rx.	Depending on SNR and SIR.
t_{DIFS}	DIFS time.	34 μs
t_{slot}	Slot time.	9 μs
CW_{min}	Minimum contention window size.	15
CW_{max}	Maximum contention window size.	1023
t_a	Airtime of LR-WPAN packets.	1.613 ms
λ	Inter-arrival time between LR-WPAN packets.	0, t_a , $9t_a$
\mathcal{M}	Set of possible MCS values.	0-7
L	Payload length per user per packet (bytes).	Variable per simulation

the received signal strength at the LR-WPAN Rx, since it is co-located with STA2, whereas d_W will change the interference power as seen by the LR-WPAN Rx.

To ensure the simulated scenarios are realistic and cover a wide range of topologies, we vary d_W such that the Wi-Fi AP’s SNR at STA1 and STA2 is within 5 dB to 45 dB, with a step of 4 dB. When the SNR is below 5 dB, the Wi-Fi receiver most likely fails to decode the packet. An SNR higher than 45 dB is generally considered unrealistic for Wi-Fi applications. Then for each d_W , a set of d_L is chosen such that the ratio of Wi-Fi signal strength and LR-WPAN signal strength (i.e., the SIR) at STA2 varies between 1 dB to 34 dB, with a step of 3 dB. We chose 1 dB as the SIR lower bound because below that, even RU puncturing cannot survive if the full packet is interfered [33], and 34 dB is set to the SIR upper bound because above this, the influence of LR-WPAN is very limited. Note that the SIR here specifically means the SIR value at the STA close to the interferer, and the CTI power in all these scenarios is too low to be detected by the CCA-ED threshold of -62 dBm at the Wi-Fi AP, hence conventional CSMA/CA will not take effect as designed.

For each scenario (two topologies, 11 SNR values and 12 SIR values), 200

Figure 5: **Spectrum occupancy of Wi-Fi and LR-WPAN.** Wi-Fi channel 1 with different RUs, which overlap with 2 MHz LR-WPAN channels 11-14.

downlink packets per STA are simulated, among which 100 packets are simulated when LR-WPAN is running on channel 12 (2410 MHz), and another 100 packets when LR-WPAN is occupying channel 13 (2415 MHz). Wi-Fi channel 1 is used, which centers at 2412 MHz, thus the LR-WPAN signal overlaps with either RU index 2 or 3 when using 4x 52-tone RUs, see Figure 5. For RU puncturing, the punctured RU is a 52-tone RU, leaving a 106-tone RU and a 52-tone RU being occupied in case of two users, and three 52-tone RUs in case of four users. Puncturing a 106-tone RU would leave a large portion of the spectrum unoccupied, whereas puncturing a 26-tone RU would result in another adjacent 26-tone RU that either still overlaps with the CTI, or cannot be easily assigned to another user.

6.3. Baseline performance

In order to quantify how much improvement a mitigation technique can bring under a specific scenario, it is important to establish some baselines. In our case, the baseline is the performance obtained when the AP uses an SU packet or MU packet (2x106 RUs) with no mitigation technique applied. The reason of choosing an SU packet is that the packet always occupies full bandwidth, hence this approach purely relies on the traditionally CSMA/CA mechanism which aims to interleave the LR-WPAN and Wi-Fi traffic in time domain. The reason of choosing MU with no mitigation measure applied is that this approach has some degree of freedom in frequency domain, but no specific measure to cope with CTI.

For the scenarios that do involve mitigation, the scheduler uses one of the techniques described in Section 4. The simulation result from the baseline scenarios and the scenarios with mitigation measure is then compared to

draw quantitative conclusions about the performance of specific mitigation techniques.

6.4. MCS selection

For MU-OFDMA, we consider that the STAs have the same traffic demands, and thus the payload length L is the same for each user. However, most well-known rate control algorithms are not directly applicable to OFDMA, as the padding required to ensure that each RU occupies the same number of OFDM symbols significantly affects performance. Therefore, a joint RU allocation and rate control algorithm is required, as also used in [27]. Furthermore, as explained in Section 2, rapid fluctuations in channel conditions due to interference lead to conservative MCS selection with slow convergence. Since the PHY-layer simulations are computationally intensive, only a limited number of packets can be simulated, whereas these rate control algorithms typically reach steady state only when the channel remains stable over a large number of packets.

To avoid these artifacts, we let the AP know the SINR each user will experience, such that an MCS based on signal quality can be selected. To determine the best MCS to choose for Wi-Fi, first the Packet Error Rate (PER) is evaluated for different SINR using an SU packet with 1000 bytes payload, which is in between the payload lengths used in the simulations. Then, at a given SINR, the highest MCS that could keep PER below 1% is used. This creates a link-level mapping between SINR and MCS.

For the mitigation techniques, we consider that the impact of CTI can be estimated as well, either by statistics from the rate control algorithm, or using feedback from the STAs. We implement this by calculating the SINR for each user when the full packet (both preamble and data) is interfered. The mitigation technique is then only applied when interference is present. To judge this in a realistic way, only when the AP starts a transmission while it senses an ongoing interference packet, the mitigation technique will be applied. In the case where interference is judged to be present, the MCS will be based on the predicted SINR, otherwise it is based on the predicted SNR.

Then, two different MCS selectors are implemented: one to optimize for total throughput and one to optimize for average latency, which are defined below in Equation 3 and 4, respectively. We employ a search method through a reduced solution space to approximate the optimal solution, which is feasible within the relatively small simulation scope considered. The MCS

distribution $\mathcal{M}^{\text{best}}$ across the number of users considered in the simulation, N_{user} , is derived by Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1 MCS selection for a certain objective function.

```

 $\mathcal{M}^{\text{max}} \leftarrow$  Max. MCS for each user based on SINR.
 $O_{\min} \leftarrow \infty$  ▷ Initialize cost function.
for each  $M_i$  in  $\mathcal{M}^{\text{max}}$  do
     $t_{\text{air}} \leftarrow$  Packet airtime based on  $M_i$  and  $L$ .
     $\mathcal{M}^c = \{M_j^c \mid M_j^c = \max(M_i, M_j^{\text{max}}), \forall j\}$ 
     $C \leftarrow |\{j \mid M_j^c \leq M_j^{\text{max}}\}|$  ▷ # of successfully served users
    Determine  $O$  based on Equation 3 or 4.
    if  $O < O_{\min}$  then
         $O_{\min} \leftarrow O$  ▷ Update best objective.
         $\mathcal{M}^{\text{best}} \leftarrow \mathcal{M}^c$  ▷ Store best MCSs.
    end if
end for

```

The reduced solution space is given by the set \mathcal{M}^{max} , which is the maximum MCS each user can tolerate based on their SINR or SNR. The scheduler then tries each of these MCS as the MCS lower bound of all users for this packet with payload length L to determine the packet airtime. If a user is expected to successfully decode the packet with the MCS used, namely, the MCS selected for this user is lower or equal to M_j^{max} (the element in the set \mathcal{M}^{max} for user $j \in \{1, \dots, N_{\text{user}}\}$), then it counts towards the objective function. The number of users that are expected to successfully decode the current packet is denoted by C . In the end, the set of MCSs $\mathcal{M}^{\text{best}}$ which leads to the minimum objective function is chosen. Note that for SU packets, the MCS will simply be the highest MCS (i.e., M_1^{max}) that allows the user to decode the packet based on its SINR. For MU, if the MCS values across users are in the same range, the minimum of \mathcal{M}^{max} is likely chosen. However, if the objective function results in a minimum even when some users are expected to be unable to decode the packet, an MCS that is not the minimum will be chosen.

For maximizing throughput, the cost function is defined in Equation 3. Namely, the throughput is the number of users that can successfully decode the packet multiplied by the packet length, divided by the airtime. The

negation sign is there because we are minimizing the objective function.

$$O_t = -\frac{C \cdot L}{t_{\text{air}}} \quad (3)$$

To minimize average latency, the MCS for each user is selected based on the cost function in Equation 4:

$$O_t = \frac{1}{N_{\text{user}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{user}}} t_{\text{air}} + (t_{\text{air}} + t_{\text{CSMA/CA}}) \cdot (\lceil \frac{j}{C} \rceil - 1). \quad (4)$$

This accounts for the fact that if the number of users that can successfully decode this packet is less than the total number of users to be served, the remaining must be served in a subsequent packet. Thus, the latency is the airtime of the current packet when a user will be served directly, otherwise the contention time $t_{\text{CSMA/CA}}$ and additional airtime of subsequent packet(s) needs to be added. The expected contention time is set to $t_{\text{CSMA/CA}} = t_{\text{DIFS}} + \frac{CW_{\text{min}}}{2} t_{\text{slot}}$. This is the expected amount of time consumed for contention following a successful transmission, which is the likely outcome given the design goal.

For simulations optimizing for the maximum total throughput, we utilize a payload length L of 1500 bytes, which is the maximum transmission unit usually used by Wi-Fi. However, applications requiring low latency like robotic control often do not carry long payloads. Therefore, we will evaluate the average latency with an MPDU length of 100 bytes, which is a realistic payload size for, e.g., communication between programmable logic controllers in an industrial setup. Since the latency will increase when an MPDU fails and needs to be retransmitted, the final average latency will depend on the specified PER level. To make a fair comparison of latency across different techniques, we set the target PER for all scenarios after retransmissions to 1%. The PER is being tracked during the simulation of a scenario. An MPDU will be retransmitted in a subsequent packet if the current PER is larger than this target, and it will be dropped when the current PER is below the threshold.

6.5. Parameters of the mitigation techniques

Given the same payload length for all users, the power boost factor is applied to equalize the SINR experienced by every user. This helps to achieve

equal MCS for all users, minimizing the need for padding. Therefore, for an RU r , its power boost factor α_r becomes:

$$\alpha_r = \max \left(0.5, \min \left(2, \sqrt[4]{10^{(\overline{\text{SINR}}_{\mathcal{R}'} - \text{SINR}_r)/10}} \right) \right), \quad (5)$$

where SINR_r is the SINR (in dB) of the RU r and $\overline{\text{SINR}}_{\mathcal{R}'}$ is the average SINR of the remaining RUs before applying the power boost factor. The bounded range accounts for the minimum and maximum power boost factor as allowed by the standard. For example, for two RUs, $r = 1$ and $r = 2$, where RU 1's initial SINR is 3 dB higher than that of RU 2, the factor between their signal powers due to the scaling factor as determined by Equation 1 becomes:

$$\frac{(s_1)^2}{(s_2)^2} = \frac{(\alpha_1)^2}{(\alpha_2)^2} \cdot \frac{\alpha_1^2 |K_1| + \alpha_2^2 |K_2|}{\alpha_1^2 |K_1| + \alpha_2^2 |K_2|} \approx \frac{\sqrt{0.5}}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot 1 \approx 0.5 \approx -3 \text{ dB}, \quad (6)$$

which thus compensates for the initial SINR difference.

For RU reallocation, the user that suffers most from the interference, as determined by their SINR when using an SU packet, will always be assigned to the RU that is the furthest away from the spectral location of the interference.

Lastly, for RU puncturing the RU where the interference is determined to be present—either by feedback from stations or CRUA—will always be punctured.

6.6. Hybrid scheduler

In addition to the static schedulers that will always choose one of the mitigation techniques, we also propose a “Hybrid” method, which attempts to choose the best technique in each scenario. First, for all techniques, it determines the MCS to use for each user by Algorithm 1. This results into various O_{\min} , i.e. the objective which is either throughput or latency, and the Hybrid scheduler chooses the technique with minimum O_{\min} . If there are multiple techniques with the same expected performance, the technique where more users are predicted to decode successfully is chosen first. If this still leads to multiple options, the technique that optimizes the lower bound of SINR across users is chosen.

The complexity of the scheduler increases with the number of users, however, in practice, the number of STAs that can participate in one OFDMA frame is limited considering that traffic needs to be available for all of them

at the same time. Furthermore, a normal OFDMA scheduler has to perform RU allocation and rate control already. The additional processing our hybrid scheduler needs to perform is considering different sets of signal qualities for each user that result from the proposed techniques.

7. Simulation results

In this section, we evaluate and discuss the results from the simulations described in the previous section. First, we show which OFDMA scheduling method leads to the highest total throughput for different scenarios. Next, we show the cumulative distribution for different SNR and SIR values of Wi-Fi, when both STAs are close to the interferer or when only one is near it. Lastly, we evaluate the impact of the different mitigation techniques on the LR-WPAN communication by looking at its PER in all scenarios.

7.1. Best technique per scenario

To evaluate the best technique per scenario, we compare the techniques to the case where the MU format is applied, but no mitigation technique is used—this is referred to as the baseline performance. Note that even though no mitigation technique is applied, it is assumed that the MCS allocator knows the SINR experienced by each user if the interference is already present at the start of the packet. The same holds for the case where SU packets are used. This means that, apart from the mitigation technique, the MCS allocator has the same SINR input when the mitigation technique is enabled or disabled, which ensures that the performance discrepancy is due to the mitigation technique itself and not due to the MCS selection.

Figure 6 shows for each of the different scenarios (i.e., controlled by STA1’s location and d_W, d_L to reach corresponding to Wi-Fi SNR and SIR) described in Section 6 which mitigation technique leads to the highest combined throughput. Among the six subplots, the top three display the result when only one STA is close to the interferer. Vertically, the left two plots show the result for continuous CTI ($\lambda = 0$), the middle ones show result for CTI with 50% duty cycle ($\lambda = t_a$), and the right ones for CTI with 10% duty cycle ($\lambda = 9t_a$). The values inside each rectangle represents the throughput difference in megabits per second of the best method as compared to no mitigation with MU packets (if no mitigation happens to perform the best for a particular scenario, the number in this grid is then the difference of

Figure 6: **Best mitigation technique per scenario for Wi-Fi throughput.** Each color indicates the best technique when only one STA (top row), or both STAs (bottom row) are close to the interferer. From left to right, the three columns of figures correspond to the case with $\lambda = 0, t_a,$ and $9t_a$. The number in the grid is the increased throughput (in Mbps) in comparison with MU packets with no mitigation measure.

the second-best technique compared to no mitigation). When multiple techniques lead to the same best performance, then multiple colors are shown in the grid. If there is no effect when comparing any mitigation measure to the baseline, it is shown in light blue.

It can be seen that SU is still the preferred option for low SIR or low SNR scenarios, this trend is especially pronounced when only one STA is close to the interferer. This can be explained by the fact that the mitigation techniques in frequency domain in these scenarios do not have sufficient signal quality to overcome the impact of the CTI. Furthermore, we analyze the probability distribution of the contention window sizes and the probability distribution of packets which (1) experience no CTI, (2) experience CTI that is detected before the packet, and (3) experience CTI that starts during the packet. For SU the CW size almost never exceeds 31 (meaning rarely two consecutive packet failures), whereas for MU, it often reaches CW_{\max} (see Figure A.13 in the Appendix). This can be explained by the fact that SU packets are generally shorter as it uses all subcarriers for one user, so there is more chance a packet fits in an interference-free period, resulting in a correctly decoded packet and thus resetting the CW size. This observation is backed by that SU packet gets more number of non-interfered packets recorded than MU, and it also has less amount of packets that experience CTI when the interference starts during the transmission (see Figure A.14 in the Appendix).

The top row of Figure 6 shows that when only one STA is close to the interferer, for an SIR higher than 18 dB and an SNR higher than 12 dB, it is beneficial to reallocate the RUs. In this way, the impact of the interference is limited by the difference in distance between the receiver and the interferer. It is interesting to see that even when CTI is at a lower duty cycle (i.e. 10%), the performance boost compared to no mitigation is still very significant in certain scenarios. One reason for this is that the LR-WPAN packets are relatively long, potentially affecting multiple Wi-Fi packets subsequently, leading to higher CW sizes even after the interference has ceased.

Next, for the scenario where both STAs are close to the interferer, the best mitigation technique at a given SNR and SIR combination is shown in the bottom row of Figure 6. It can be seen that RU reallocation is rarely chosen, because all STAs are at the same location. Here RU puncturing is beneficial in most of the scenarios as it is most effective to avoid packet errors, while power boost factor is the best for rather high SIR and SNR values, i.e. above 25 dB SIR and 30 dB SNR. The latter needs high SIR values to be able

to overcome the interference, and high SNR values to limit the impact of reduced power on the remaining RU due to Eq. 1. The reason that mitigation measures have no effect at low SIR values for a duty cycle of 100% (indicated by cyan in the bottom left plot of Figure 6) is that the throughput remains zero no matter which technique or no technique is applied. This is because Wi-Fi relies on the full bandwidth preamble (referred to as the legacy preamble) for packet detection and synchronization. The legacy preamble cannot benefit from the OFDMA based CTI mitigation technique, which only takes effect on the Wi-Fi 6 preamble and the data payload. If CTI is continuous and too strong, packet detection error and synchronization error will appear in the legacy preamble, hence whatever mitigation comes after this is too late to rescue the packet.

We have also performed simulation for the best mitigation techniques when optimizing for the average latency using a payload length L of 100 bytes, which leads to very similar observation as the throughput, and is shown in Figure A.15 in the Appendix. In various scenarios, a latency reduction of more than 6 ms is obtained compared to no mitigation. One difference is that for the case where both STAs are close to the interferer, SU is generally not a good choice as it leads to large contention window sizes, which increases latency, whereas for MU this effect is limited as it serves two users at once with less contention overhead.

7.2. Overall performance per technique

To analyze the overall performance of each mitigation technique, we present the cumulative distribution of the total throughput and latency in Figure 7 and Figure 8 respectively. The cumulative distribution covers the previously discussed individual cases, namely the location of STA1 (close or far from interferer), and scenarios with all combinations of SNR and SIR experienced by STA2 under the same average CTI duty cycle. For conciseness, we only show the results obtained for 50% CTI duty cycle in Figure 7. In the figure, a value of 0.5 at 6 Mbps means the total throughput in 50% of the scenarios is at most 6 Mbps. We show the performance of the mitigation techniques by color coded firm lines, and additional benchmarks by dash or dotted lines. In particular, the dotted blue and cyan lines indicate the performance of SU and MU, when no interference is present. This defines the upper bound of the throughput. Then the dashed blue and cyan lines

Figure 7: **Cumulative distribution of the total throughput across all scenarios.** Each color represents a different mitigation technique under average 50% CTI duty cycle, or no CTI (thick dotted lines).

indicate the performance of SU and MU when the MCS selector only takes SNR into account, but it is ignorant of the interference.

In general, it can be seen that none of the techniques can reach the performance when no interference is present, and there usually is a large gap. This is due to the fact that even with mitigation, the applied MCS with interference is still often lower than what can be applied without interference. In case of RU puncturing, it directly reduces the bandwidth for Wi-Fi. Furthermore, there are cases where even with mitigation technique, packets cannot survive. Overall speaking, it can be seen that the “Hybrid” method results in a higher total throughput than “No mitigation”, and in various scenarios it leads to a significant improvement of more than 30 Mbps. Out of the three mitigation techniques, it is usually either RU puncturing or RU reallocation that results in the best performance. It is interesting to see that SU without knowledge about the interference in some rare cases performs better than with this knowledge. Even though the CTI-aware scheduler has lower packet loss, the CTI-unaware scheduler uses a higher MCS, leading to lower airtime per packet. This then leads to more cases where an interference-free packet

Figure 8: **Cumulative distribution of the average latency across all scenarios.** Each color represents a different mitigation technique under average 50% CTI duty cycle, or no CTI (thick dotted lines).

can be sent, and a higher throughput is observed in some cases.

Next, we show the cumulative distribution when the scheduler is configured to achieve minimum average latency, also using $\lambda = t_a$ (i.e., 50% CTI duty cycle) in Figure 8. The closer the curve is to the top left, the better the performance across all scenarios, since latency is desired to stay low. Also here it can be seen that the mitigation options cannot fully compensate for the performance loss caused by interference, although it is closer to the case without interference in more scenarios, namely around 40%. Here it can be seen that for both SU and MU without mitigation, the performance is usually better when the MCS is adapted based on SINR, as compared to the case where it is unaware of the CTI. In several scenarios, SU is the best option, as explained in Section 7.1. On the contrary, in case both STAs are close to the interferer, SU performs much worse, because a part of the subcarriers of the user will always be affected, while for MU it only affects one of the users.

For the evaluation of the three mitigation techniques, RU puncturing generally achieves the best performance in terms of average latency, as it is

Figure 9: **Cumulative distribution of LR-WPAN PER across all scenarios.** Each color represents a different mitigation technique.

particularly well suited to minimizing packet errors. While RU reallocation is beneficial in case only one STA is close to the interferer, it does not improve latency for the other half of the scenarios (i.e. both STAs close to the interference), and therefore its overall performance improvement is limited. Power boost factor only shows improvement in a limited number of scenarios as compared to MU with no mitigation, which is when the SIR is high enough to overcome it with an increase in power.

7.3. Impact on LR-WPAN communication

In order to observe the impact of Wi-Fi OFDMA based CTI mitigation on the LR-WPAN network, we evaluate its PER in both topologies from Figure 4 with $\lambda = t_a$, obtained from all the previous simulations. In order to control the duty cycle, the LR-WPAN transmitters do not apply CCA and will thus transmit regardless of an ongoing Wi-Fi transmission, which happens in a hidden-node scenario or for techniques based on LR-WPAN that do not use CCA (like 6TiSCH). The cumulative distribution of the LR-WPAN PER for all simulated scenarios is shown in Figure 9.

First, it can be seen that in about 40% of the cases, the LR-WPAN communication does not suffer from the Wi-Fi interference. On the other hand,

there are also cases where the LR-WPAN communication cannot survive at all, which is also in about 40% of the cases for MU without mitigation technique (see red line). Next, it can be seen that RU reallocation and MU follow more or less the same distribution. This is to be expected as these options have similar influence on the LR-WPAN communication, because the AP always sends full bandwidth signals without power boosting. Using power boost factor leads to a slightly higher LR-WPAN PER, because the interfering Wi-Fi power experienced by LR-WPAN is higher. SU leads to a decrease in PER of LR-WPAN as compared to MU without mitigation, which can be explained by the fact that SU packets have on average a lower airtime and more idle gaps in between, enlarging the chance of non-overlapped LR-WPAN communication. RU puncturing, on the other hand, improves the PER of LR-WPAN significantly, since the data part of the Wi-Fi packet does not occupy the spectrum the LR-WPAN communication uses. This is mostly in the case where either the power of Wi-Fi is significant (small d_W), or the LR-WPAN SNR is rather low (large d_L). For both high Wi-Fi power (small d_W) and low LR-WPAN SNR (large d_L), SU is better because it results in more idle time, while RU puncturing cannot fully prevent LR-WPAN packet errors due to the full-bandwidth Wi-Fi preamble.

To summarize, throughput and latency simulations show that the scenario influences which mitigation technique is the best to choose. RU reallocation is beneficial at relatively high SNR and when STAs experience different interference levels. RU puncturing, on the other hand, is the best choice for medium-level SIR (≈ 15 dB to 25 dB), while RU reallocation should be used at high SIR. A hybrid scheduler can consistently choose the best method, resulting in a throughput increase of more than 30 Mbps, and a reduction in latency of 6 ms in various scenarios. Furthermore, RU puncturing can successfully reduce the PER of the interfering communication as well, while per-RU power boost only slightly increases LR-WPAN's PER.

8. Experimental validation

After the evaluation of mitigation techniques based on simulation, we select the two best techniques for experimental validation. In this section, we will discuss and analyze the implementation of RU reallocation and RU puncturing using an AP that runs *openwifi*. As STAs, we utilize the ESP32-

C6 microprocessor, which includes a Wi-Fi 6 chip. Next to that, two LR-WPAN transmitters (Zolertia RE-Mote) are used.

8.1. Implementation

We use openwifi [4], a full-stack IEEE 802.11 transceiver running on a System-on-Chip, consisting of a Field Programmable Gate Array (FPGA) and ARM processor. The baseband processing and lower MAC-layer is implemented on the FPGA, whereas the driver and higher-level MAC run as Linux kernel modules on the ARM processor. In our previous works [39], we extended it with OFDMA support. When running as AP, the RU allocation can be controlled from the driver, which allows us to implement the RU reallocation technique.

CRUA is implemented on the FPGA by expanding the use of the existing 256-point FFT core used in the FPGA for decoding the IEEE 802.11ax data symbols. When the receiver is idle, the FFT core is used to calculate the average squared magnitude of the subcarriers within an RU, i.e. its average power. Then, when considering a certain RU allocation, it determines whether one of the RUs has a considerable higher average power than the others as described by Equation 2. If the threshold of CRUA is met for one of the RUs, this will be signaled to the transmitter module on the FPGA, such that upon preparing the packet, it can puncture this RU. Puncturing is implemented by denoting the STA identifier to 2046 (as required by the standard) and nullifying the corresponding subcarriers. Furthermore, a scaling factor is applied on the remaining RUs following Equation 1 to keep the total transmit power constant before and after RU puncturing.

8.1.1. RU reallocation

In [34], we evaluated the performance of RU reallocation as compared to a naive scheduler, as well as a scheduler that only uses SU packets. The naive scheduler uses a fixed RU allocation that assigns an RU to a user where it experiences narrowband CTI. In those experiments, the duty cycle is fixed, while in this experiment, we evaluate the performance of RU reallocation in different measurements with a duty cycle of 0%, 10%, 50% and 100%, similar to the simulations of Section 7.1.

Knowing that it is very hard to control CTI duty cycle with real LR-WPAN communication, since the duty cycle of the interference may also change depending on Wi-Fi network's activity, we generate the waveform of an IEEE 802.15.4 packet in MATLAB, which is replayed by the R&S[®]

CMW270 Wireless Connectivity Tester. The signal is sampled at 20MHz and transmitted using a carrier frequency of 2412 MHz. We therefore shifted the signal to IEEE 802.15.4 channel 11, which overlaps with the first 106-tone RU of Wi-Fi channel 1. The AP uses a fixed MCS 7, which is the best MCS that can be used in the created scenario. To create different duty cycles, the repeatedly transmitted IQ samples are appended with a period of zeros. The output power of the tester is set to -60 dBm, in order to establish CTI only at STA2, while both STAs are in close proximity to the AP to compensate for its limited transmit power. Hence, the experiment covers the simulation scenario of Figure 4, in relatively high SNR (20 dB to 30 dB) and SIR (≈ 20 dB) values.

ESP32-C6 devices are used as Wi-Fi stations, and the openwifi AP has prior knowledge of the RU allocation it should use. This is because under high CTI duty cycle, Wi-Fi PER deteriorates, which affects the CTI feedback towards AP. One of the stations is placed right next to the tester’s output port, while the other is placed on the other side around 0.5 m away, with the AP in the middle. We use iPerf to transmit UDP packets using the default payload length of 1470 bytes to the two STAs simultaneously. Five measurements of one minute are performed for each scheduler at each duty cycle, and the average throughput as reported by the STAs is noted.

See Figure 10 for the average throughput for each STA with error bars showing standard deviation, influenced by CTI at different duty cycles. The dotted lines correspond to the STA that is close to the interferer (STA1), while the solid lines show the throughput for the STA that is further away from it. First of all, the throughput when using only SU is lower, which can be partly attributed to the increased overhead from the preamble and additional contention time. Furthermore, it can be observed that, compared to the case with no CTI (0% duty cycle), the throughput towards STA2 decreases for both SU and the naive scheduler, meaning these techniques cannot effectively mitigate the CTI. This decrease is more pronounced at higher duty cycles; for example, the naive method shows a 39% throughput reduction at a 50% duty cycle and nearly 100% at a 100% CTI duty cycle. In contrast, when using RU reallocation, the throughput to both STAs remains roughly constant across different duty cycle settings. This proves that RU reallocation is highly effective for mitigating CTI in scenarios with unequal interference power levels for the STAs. It also corresponds to the simulation result, where under high 100% duty cycle, almost 100% throughput increase (≈ 40 Mbps) can be obtained using RU reallocation under high SNR and SIR,

Figure 10: **Experimental result of throughput under varying CTI duty cycle.** Each color represents a different OFDMA scheduler, for the scenario where one STA is close to the interferer.

and the impact reduces for lower duty cycle.

8.1.2. RU puncturing

For the influence of RU puncturing on both Wi-Fi and LR-WPAN traffic, we refer to our previous work [33], where we experimentally show the performance of punctured single-user uplink packets using trigger frames. While in [33] it is assumed that interference is always present, here we demonstrate the capability of CRUA for real-time RU puncturing, namely an RU is only punctured if an ongoing LR-WPAN packet is detected on this RU. We will evaluate the execution time of CRUA for RU puncturing in terms of the required detection and scheduling latency.

8.1.3. Execution time of RU puncturing

To assess the real-time performance, it is important to consider the HE PPDU (High-Efficiency Physical layer Protocol Data Unit) structure as used by IEEE 802.11ax in Figure 11.

In terms of detection latency for the puncturing decision, at a sampling rate of 20 MHz, Wi-Fi 6 requires 256 samples for an FFT operation, hence the

Figure 11: **Wi-Fi HE PPDU structure with durations per field.** Annotations clarify the real-time performance assessment of CRUA for RU puncturing.

duration to collect samples for one FFT is $12.8 \mu\text{s}$. Afterwards, the CRUA calculation takes $3.05 \mu\text{s}$. Thus, in total when a CTI packet has started at least $15.85 \mu\text{s}$ before preparing a Wi-Fi packet, it can be avoided by RU puncturing. Since the DIFS is $34 \mu\text{s}$, and the inter-packet gap becomes even longer when random back-off is performed, this usually gives enough time to perform CRUA in between two Wi-Fi packets, even in a saturated channel.

When the CRUA decision is taken, the to-be-transmitted packet has to be prepared and delivered to the RF front-end. The time between the decision and the actual start of the packet on the air is measured to be $4.9 \mu\text{s}$ as denoted in Figure 11. Since the start of the packet still occupies the full bandwidth, RU puncturing has no effect yet here. Using one HE SIG-B symbol, which suffices for two users, the full-bandwidth preamble takes $36 \mu\text{s}$. So, if the CTI packet has already stopped within $40.9 \mu\text{s}$ after the CRUA decision, RU puncturing would be unnecessary, as the CTI does not last till the Wi-Fi data part. Considering that narrowband packets like LR-WPAN can take from around 0.5 ms up to 50 ms , we judge that the chance of unnecessary puncturing is low.

8.1.4. Demonstration

Next, we use the Anritsu MS2690A spectrum analyzer to capture packets transmitted by the openwifi AP to the two STAs, while simultaneously the two LR-WPAN devices are exchanging packets. The openwifi AP operates with 20 MHz bandwidth at Wi-Fi channel 1, which centers at 2412 MHz , and the LR-WPAN transmitters use channel 14, which centers at 2420 MHz . The spectrum analyzer is set to a center frequency of 2412 MHz with a span of 25 MHz . Figure 12 shows the captured spectrogram when a LR-WPAN packet starts transmitting (left spectrogram) shortly before the AP starts its downlink transmission. The right spectrogram shows when the LR-WPAN packet ends. It can be seen that immediately after CRUA detects the CTI,

Figure 12: **Spectrograms captured during a real-time RU puncture.** CRUA enables changing a 106-tone RU to a 52-tone RU, when a LR-WPAN packet starts (left) and ends (right). The horizontal axis is time and vertical axis is frequency, centered at 2412 MHz with 25 MHz span.

it switches from a 2x 106-tone MU packet to one with 1x 106-tone and 2x 52-tone RUs, among which one 52-tone RU is punctured to avoid LR-WPAN interference. Then, when the LR-WPAN packet ends, the scheduler switches back to the original RU allocation for the next packet.

It can be seen that the legacy preamble is still transmitted on the full 20 MHz bandwidth for backward compatibility. Thus, this still causes a short period of interference on the LR-WPAN packet. The work in [11] showed the impact of the Wi-Fi preamble on ZigBee transmissions. First they argue that when it interferes with the ZigBee preamble, which is 128 μ s long, it does not affect the ZigBee transmission much due to the redundancy of its preamble. When the Wi-Fi preamble interferes with a ZigBee data symbol long enough, it will affect its decoding ability, but [11] shows this can be effectively mitigated by applying Reed-Solomon error correction codes in the ZigBee packets. Our simulation results in Section 7.3 and our previous work [33] also show that even with RU puncturing, Wi-Fi still has an impact on LR-WPAN PER, due to the full bandwidth preamble. On the other hand, the Wi-Fi legacy preamble is thus also interfered by LR-WPAN, but since the fields in the Wi-Fi preamble use the most robust modulation and coding scheme, and channel estimation for the data part is performed using the partial-bandwidth HE preamble fields, the impact of Zigbee on Wi-Fi is acceptable. This conclusion aligns with [33] and the simulations in Section 7.

In short, we have validated experimentally the applicability of RU reallocation. Its performance is compared to no mitigation for different CTI duty

cycle, i.e., showing to eliminate 39% of throughput loss at 50% duty cycle. Furthermore, we have shown that CRUA can assist the RU puncturing decision with a sensing time of only 15.85 μs , which is achieved in an idle period of the Wi-Fi transceiver. The spectrogram also shows that even if RU puncturing is applied timely, the LR-WPAN packet still has a portion interfered by the full-bandwidth Wi-Fi preamble, though the impact of this is easily mitigated, proven by various prior arts and our simulations.

9. Conclusion

In this work, several IEEE 802.11ax standard-compliant CTI mitigation techniques are proposed by making use of OFDMA. The first technique applies a power boost factor per RU to overcome the interference. The second technique performs RU reallocation across users, which means assigning an affected RU to a user that experiences less interference power compared to another user. Finally, RU puncturing can be used to avoid carrying data on an affected RU, which will also limit the impact on the interferer's communication. The mitigation requires information about CTI's presence, which involves either detecting CTI at stations and report the CTI back to the AP, or performing a real-time CCA per RU (CRUA) at the AP, to avoid an ongoing interference packet.

Simulations are performed to evaluate the performance of each technique in terms of total throughput and average latency, and to find out the scenarios in which a technique is most beneficial. A hybrid scheduler can reach more than 30 Mbps throughput increase and 6 ms latency reduction compared to no mitigation in several scenarios.

Real-life experiments using the SDR platform openwifi and commercial Wi-Fi 6 stations show the feasibility and advantage of RU reallocation, capable of eliminating 39% of throughput reduction due to CTI at 50% duty cycle. Finally, the implementation of CRUA with detection latency of 15.85 μs has been shown, in order to perform RU puncturing using openwifi. A spectrogram capture proves that our AP with CRUA assistance can puncture the correct RU to avoid CTI and revert the RU allocation once the CTI packet is over.

For future work, considering that OFDMA scheduling is already a multi-dimensional problem, and the complexity increases even more when CTI is considered and by using multi-RU in Wi-Fi 7, it would be interesting to utilize machine learning techniques to solve this problem. It is also intriguing

to benchmark the machine learning based approach against the heuristic methods, especially considering real-time constraints. Furthermore, instead of using static inter-arrival times for CTI traffic, stochastic or event-based traffic generation could also be examined. Ideally, realistic PHY-layer aspects would be integrated with advanced MAC-layer implementations as present in ns-3. Another aspect for future work is the experimental validation of power boost factor, possibly in combination with RU reallocation. Finally, we also foresee to investigate the method of SIR estimation at the stations per RU, which can assist the AP with MCS allocation in OFDMA scheduling.

Glossary

AP	Access Point
BLE	Bluetooth Low Energy
CCA	Clear Channel Assessment
CRUA	Clear Resource Unit Assessment
CSI	Channel State Information
CSMA/CA	Carrier Sense Multiple Access with Collision Avoidance
CTI	Cross-Technology Interference
CW	Contention Window
DCF	Distributed Coordination Function
DCM	Dual Carrier Modulation
DIFS	DCF Inter-Frame Space
ED	Energy Detection
FPGA	Field-Programmable Gate Array
LR-WPAN	Low-Rate Wireless Personal Area Network
MAC	Medium Access Control
MCS	Modulation and Coding Scheme
MPDU	MAC Protocol Data Unit
MU	Multi-User
OFDMA	Orthogonal Frequency Division Multiple Access
PER	Packet Error Rate

QAM	Quadrature Amplitude Modulation
RU	Resource Unit
SD	Signal Detection
SDR	Software-Defined Radio
SIFS	Short Inter-Frame Space
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SIR	Signal-to-Interference Ratio
SISO	Single-Input Single-Output
SNR	Signal-to-Noise Ratio
STA	Station
SU	Single User
TDMA	Time-Division Multiple Access
UORA	Uplink OFDMA Random Access
WLAN	Wireless Local Area Networks

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Thijs Havinga: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Software, Investigation, Validation, Writing - Original Draft. **Xianjun Jiao:** Investigation, Validation, Resources, Writing - Review & Editing. **Wei Liu:** Validation, Visualization, Writing - Review & Editing. **Baiheng Chen** and **Robbe Gaeremynck:** Validation, Writing - Review & Editing. **Ingrid Moerman:** Supervision, Writing - Review & Editing, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used Microsoft Copilot and ChatGPT in order to enhance the readability of the manuscript. After using these tools, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are included within the manuscript.

Appendix A. Additional results

Figure A.13: **Histograms of the CW size when optimizing for throughput.** Each plot is a different mitigation technique, scenario is where one STA is close to the interferer at 10% CTI duty cycle.

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Figure A.14: **Breakdown of CTI detection for all packets during simulation.** Evaluated for the simulation of Figure 6 at 10% CTI duty cycle. Green represents packets with no CTI, red represents packets where CTI is detected and blue where CTI is not detected. Each plot represents a different mitigation technique.

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Figure A.15: **Best mitigation technique per scenario for Wi-Fi latency.** Each color indicates the best technique when only one STA (top row), or both STAs (bottom row) are close to the interferer. From left to right, the three columns of figures correspond to the case with $\lambda = 0, t_a,$ and $9t_a$. The number in the square is the reduction in latency (in ms) compared to MU packets with no mitigation measure.

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